

NOTES

Even when compounds 8 and 9 were included, the following equation with a good correlation coefficient could be obtained.

$$\nu_{\text{C-O stretch}} = 1202 + 26.7 \Sigma \sigma \quad (2)$$

$$n = 7,$$

$$r = 0.97$$

The correlation coefficients of equations (1) and (2) are quite significant, but the result should be considered only indicative since the compounds under consideration are quite few.

The phosphoryl vibration of the parent compound *O,O*-bisphenyl isopropyl phosphonate appears as a doublet where two adjacent vibrations at 1280 and 1255 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to this vibration, were observed. This doublet was observed in cases of all compounds except 13 and 15. Earlier investigators had concluded that the doublets can arise from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibrations⁵ or due to the accidental proximity of a band ascribed to different vibrations in the molecule⁶. It was found that when the doublet is characterised by small differences in frequency and intensity between component peaks and when the doublet is not being fully resolved, these arose from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibration³. By contrast, in those spectra in which the doublet arose from accidental proximity of a band ascribed to a different vibration in the molecule, the peaks were separated maximum upto 50 cm^{-1} with a well defined minimum between them³. In the case of bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates presently investigated, there appears no well-defined minimum between adjacent peaks, and the frequency between the peaks varies from 20 to 40 cm^{-1} . In many cases they are characterised by small differences in intensity, sometimes not being fully resolved (compounds 13–15). Therefore, it can be concluded that the doublets arose from two conformers with different phosphoryl vibration frequencies and not from accidental proximity of a band ascribed to a different vibration.

An absorption band at 1300 cm^{-1} in the case of bisaryl methyl phosphonates and other compounds⁷ containing P–Me groups were ascribed to P–C stretching by some workers⁷. The absence of any such peak at 1300 cm^{-1} for bisaryl isopropyl phosphonates confirms the view that these were normal C–H deformation vibrations the frequency of which has been perturbed by the presence of phosphorus³.

References

1. E. S. J. NIDIRY and N. K. ROY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27** 1024.
2. E. S. J. NIDIRY and N. K. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989 **66** 230.
3. L. C. THOMAS, "Interpretation of Infrared Spectra of Organophosphorus Compounds", Heydon and Sons, 1974, pp. 11-95.
4. H. H. JAFFE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 191.
5. F. S. MORTIMER, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1957, **9**, 270.

6. L. J. BELLAMY and L. BEECHER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1701.
7. K. VASU and N. K. ROY, *Agric. Biol. Chem.*, 1983, **47**, 2657.

¹³C NMR and Crystallographic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance in 2-Alkylanisoles

V. BALIAH* and V. PREMASAGAR

Piem's Laboratory, 79 Venkatanagar, Pondicherry-605 011
 Manuscript received 28 June 1990, accepted 1 August 1990

ALTHOUGH steric enhancement of resonance (SER) has been studied in 4-nitro-2-substituted-anisoles¹, 4-acetyl-2-substituted-anisoles² and other 2,4-substituted anisoles³, its existence in 2-alkylanisoles has not been made known. When a powerful electron-withdrawing substituent is present *para* to the methoxyl, the resonance interaction between the *para*-substituents will be high and the enhancement of resonance caused by a substituent like methyl or a halogen atom *ortho* to the methoxyl is considerable. Its detection in such cases is also easy. In the absence of a powerful electron-attracting group *para* to the methoxyl, the SER caused by an *ortho*-substituent will be feeble and its detection requires more exact observations and more sophisticated experimental measurements. For example, Dhami and Stothers⁴ failed to observe it in the ¹³C nmr spectra of 2-alkylanisoles and they even expressed doubt about the existence of SER.

We now have convincing evidence for the SER in 2-alkylanisoles from the ¹³C nmr data published by Schuster *et al.*⁵ recently. The data are given in Table 1. It may be seen that all the 2-alkylanisoles (2–5; Table 1), show increased electron

TABLE 1—SCS-CORRECTED^a ¹³C CHEMICAL SHIFTS^b OF THE *para*-CARBON IN SUBSTITUTED-ANISOLE^s*

Compd. no.	Substituent	δ
1	Nil	120.64
2	2-Methyl	120.04
3	2-Ethyl	120.12
4	2- <i>i</i> -Propyl	120.30
5	2- <i>t</i> -Butyl	120.29
6	2,6-Dimethyl	123.39
7	2,6-Diethyl	123.53
8	2,6-Di- <i>i</i> -propyl	123.86
9	2,6-Di- <i>t</i> -butyl	122.91
10	2- <i>t</i> -Butyl-6-methyl	122.49

*Data from Ref. 5.

^aObtained by subtracting the substituent chemical shift (SCS) of the *meta*-oriented alkyl group R or groups R and R (with reference to C₄) from the experimental value. SCS = $\delta \{^{13}\text{C}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{R})\} - 128.31$ ppm (L. Ernst, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1974, 3079). ^bIn ppm from Me₄Si.

density at the C-4 carbon atom (upfield shift) compared with anisole due to enhanced resonance. In

contrast, the di-*ortho*-substituted-anisoles (6–10) show decreased electron density (downfield shift) compared with anisole. These chemical shifts leave no doubt regarding the existence of SER in 2–5 and steric inhibition of resonance in 6–10 (Table 1).

The above view gets further support from the structural parameters (Table 2) obtained for sub-

TABLE 2—SELECTED STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS* OF SUBSTITUTED-ANISIC ACIDS*

Compd. no.	Substituent	C ₁ —OCH ₃	O—CH ₃	C ₁ —O—CH ₃ angle degrees
		bond length	bond length	
		Å		
1	R ₁ =R ₂ =H	1.356	1.435	118.1
2	R ₁ = <i>t</i> -Bu, R ₂ =H	1.347	1.445	120.8
3	R ₁ =R ₂ =Me	1.381	1.417	115.5
4	R ₁ =R ₂ = <i>i</i> -Pr	1.388	1.425	114.0
5	R ₁ =R ₂ = <i>t</i> -Bu	1.374	1.424	116.5

*Data from Ref. 5.

stituted anisic acids from crystallographic measurements⁶. The shortening of the C₁—O bond and the increase in the C₁—O—CH₃ angle of the mono-substituted-*t*-Bu compound (2) compared with unsubstituted anisic acid (1; Table 2) indicate enhancement of resonance in it. The lengthening of the C₁—O bond and the decrease in C₁—O—CH₃ angle in the 2,6-disubstituted compounds (3–5; Table 2) compared with anisic acid indicate steric inhibition of resonance in them. Increased resonance (SER) of the methoxyl increases the double bond character of the C₁—O bond and shortens the bond; the C₁—O—CH₃ bond angle also increases due to increased sp² hybridisation of the σ-bonding electrons of oxygen. Decreased resonance increases the C₁—O bond length and decreases the C₁—O—CH₃ angle.

Schuster *et al.*⁵ used the data (Tables 1 and 2) for a different purpose. They made no reference to steric enhancement of resonance in 2-alkylanisoles.

References

- V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1960, 21; K. GANAPATHY, T. BALASUBRAMANIAN and K. PANDIARAJAN, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 1114; V. BALIAH and J. J. DIANA, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1988, **100**, 287.
- V. BALIAH and V. SUNDARI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 804; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1989, **101**, 33; V. BALIAH, V. PREMASAGAR, R. KRISHNAKUMAR and R. JEYARAMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, **27**, 151.
- V. BALIAH and V. M. KANAGASABAPATHY, *Tetrahedron*, 1978, **34**, 3611; V. BALIAH, K. GANAPATHY and T. BALASUBRAMANIAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 983; V. BALIAH and B. THEYMOLI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, **16**, 509, 1029; K. GANAPATHY and P. JEYAGANDHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1036; V. BALIAH and P. V. V. SATYANARAYANA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1980, **19**, 619; M. UMA and C. S. KALAVATHI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 412; V. BALIAH, A. MANGALAMUDAIYAR and T. RAVI, *Curr. Sci.*, 1983, **57**, 793; V. BALIAH, B. THEYMOLI and A. MANGALAMUDAIYAR, *Curr. Sci.*, 1989, **58**, 738.

- K. S. DHAMI and J. B. STOTHERS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44**, 2855.
- I. I. SCHUSTER, M. PARVEZ and A. J. FREYER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1988, **53**, 5819.

Negative Ion Mass Spectra of Coumarin Derivatives†

K. P. MADHUSUDANAN*, VIJAI LAKSHMI,

F. A. HUSSAINI and A. SHOEB

Medicinal Chemistry Division, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

Manuscript received 19 February 1990, accepted 3 July 1990

IDENTIFICATION and structure elucidation of coumarins are done with the aid of spectral techniques. The mass spectral fragmentation patterns of coumarins and related compounds have been reviewed¹. Metastable and collisional activation spectra have also been used for the differentiation of isomeric coumarins². However, there are only a very few reports on the negative ion mass spectra

†CDRI communication no. 4581.